

On Magnetic Birefringence in Mercuri- sulphosalicylic Acid Sols.

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The sols and gels of mercurisulphosalicylic acid have been studied by us in previous publications (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 367). It was observed there that by coagulating 1% sol of mercurisulphosalicylic acid with electrolytes, translucent or opaque jellies are obtained which undergo marked syneresis. We have now been successful in obtaining water-like transparent jellies by coagulating 2% sol. Mercurisulphosalicylic acid was prepared in the same way as described in the previous paper by dissolving well washed freshly precipitated mercuric oxide in 5-sulphosalicylic acid; the gelatinous white mass thus obtained was then dried on a water-bath. The following concentrations for the transparent jellies would be of interest.

TABLE I.

Mercurisulphosalicylic acid soln. (2%) = 3 c.c. Total vol. = 5 c.c.

Amount of $N/2\text{-KNO}_3$.	Observations.
0.2 c. c.	Perfectly transparent jelly in 25 hr.
0.4	Transparent jelly in 18 hr.
0.7	Transparent jelly accompanied with slight opalescence in 15 hr.

By increasing the concentrations of potassium nitrate, the time of setting decreases, whilst the opalescence increases. However, it was observed by Wo. Ostwald and Mertens (*Koll. Chem Beih.*, 1926, 23, 242) that mercurisulphosalicylic acid loses its colloidal nature in presence of chloride ions. The influence of chloride ions on the time of setting of this jelly are given in Table II.

TABLE II.

Amount of sol (2%) = 3 c.c. Total vol. = 5 c.c. $N/2\text{-KNO}_3 = 1.03$ c.c.

Time of setting (min.)	...	30	3	7	20	960	No jelly
Amount of $N/10\text{-KCl}$ (c.c.)...		0	0.3	0.35	0.4	0.45	1.0

From these results, it would be seen that the presence of small amounts of potassium chloride sensitises the sol and the jelly is very readily obtained, while the dissolving influence begins only at a later stage. The influence of halide ions on the stability of the colloidal phase of mercurisulphosalicylic acid can be very well studied from the view point of the magnetic birefringence exhibited by the particles of this sol and hence in the present communication an attempt has been made to investigate this property of the sol under various conditions.

The phenomenon of magnetic birefringence was for the first time observed by Majorana (*R.Acad. Linci.*, 1902, *v*, 11, 374, 463, 531) and it has been investigated by Freundlich and co-workers, Bjornstahl and others in the case of vanadium pentoxide, gold, silver, platinum and other sols. Berkman and Zocher (*Kolloid Z.*, 1927, 42, 309, 322) observed that mercurisulphosalicylic acid exhibits the property of double refraction when in the state of flow and moreover, it is also doubly refractive when placed in an electric or magnetic field. The results of magnetic double refraction being a measure of the optical and magnetic anisotropies of the colloidal particles, are of considerable interest. Zocher and Berkman's results (*loc. cit.*) are only qualitative so far as the magnetic birefringence is concerned and as such the present study of the subject has been undertaken.

The experimental arrangement was similar to that described by Chinchalkar (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1931, 6, 165). A point-o-lite lamp of 1000 c. p. was used as a source, the light from which condensed and collimated before passing through the polariser of which the principal direction of vibration was inclined at 45° to the horizontal. The direction of the magnetic field as well as the neutral axis was horizontal. The sol to be investigated was placed in 33 cm. long tubes between the two poles of an electromagnet, the poles being 33 cm. wide. A long glass strip under pressure or strain was used as a compensator. The strip bent in its own plane would produce different layers above and below the neutral axis which will behave like a series of uni-axial positive and negative crystals with their axes

parallel to the neutral axis. The beam of the plane polarised light after being allowed to pass through this compensator strip is examined with a crossed nicol and a telescope attached to an Adam-Hilger micrometer eye-piece. In all the cases, a current of 3 amperes was passed through the electromagnet producing a field of 6500 gauss which was sufficient to cause marked shifts in the dark band. Nitrobenzene along with the same strained compensator was used as a standard for comparison. The readings in terms of micrometer scale are given below.

The Influence of Dilution.

The Cotton-Mouton constant for nitrobenzene has been regarded as 100 for comparison, and the values have been expressed relative to it. In the given field with the same compensator, the shift observed in the case of nitrobenzene corresponded to 108 divisions on the micrometer scale.

To some extent, the values also depend on the mode of preparing the solution of the colloid which gives particles of different dispersity, and as such in one set of experiments, one and the same sol was used. A mean of six readings was usually taken for shifts.

TABLE III.

Sol conc. (%)	...	2.0	1.0	0.5	0.4
Shift (micrometer scale)	...	100	63	28	19.5
Relative birefringence	...	92.6	58.4	25.9	18.1

These results show that in the case of this sol, the birefringence is approximately proportional to the concentration of the sol. The anomaly is more marked in the first dilutions.

TABLE IV.

Influence of Potassium Chloride.

To 10 c.c. of 2% sol varying amounts of N/10-KCl were added and the total volume was made up to 20 c.c. by adding water.

N/10-KCl	...	0	0.5	1.0	3.0
Shift	...	63	44	32	21
Relative birefringence	...	58.4	40.6	29.6	19.4

Thus as the concentration of potassium chloride is increased, the magnetic birefringence of the colloidal solution is decreased. This corresponds to the dissolving influence of chloride ions as observed by Wo. Ostwald and Martens (*loc. cit.*).

TABLE V.

Influence of Potassium Bromide.

To 10 c.c. of 2% sol varying amounts of N/35-KBr were added and the total volume was made up to 20 c.c.

KBr (c.c.) ...	0	0.5	1.0	2.0	3.0	5.0	10.0
Shift ...	47	41	35	48	63	82	175
Relative birefringence ...	43.5	38.0	32.4	44.3	58.3	75.9	162.0

It will be seen from these readings, that in the presence of small quantities of potassium bromide, the anisotropy of the particles decreases, but after a concentration, the value begins to rise and goes to a considerably high length. According to the observation of Wo. Ostwald and Mertens (*loc. cit.*), the addition of bromide ions, similar to chloride ions, should bring out the dissolution of the colloidal phase. Our results on birefringence, however, show that this dissolution is only brought about at lower concentrations of bromide ions. That the sol undergoes coagulation at higher concentrations of bromide in much less time is also seen from the following results on jelly formation of the sol under the influence of bromide ions.

Amount of sol = 3 c.c. Total vol. = 5 c.c.

N/2-KBr (c.c.) ...	1.4	1.5	1.6
Time of setting ...	80'	30'	30''

TABLE VI.

Influence of Potassium Nitrate.

Amount of 2% sol = 10 c.c. Total vol. = 20 c.c.

N/20-KNO ₃ (c.c.) ...	0	1.0	2.0	3.0	4.0
Shift ..	47	58	71	101	132
Relative birefringence ...	43.5	53.7	65.7	93.5	122

Influence of Barium Nitrate.

It could not be possible to study magnetic birefringence with higher concentrations of barium nitrate because the sol developed opalescence. The excessive scattering not only diminished the intensity of light but also caused the depolarisation and hence it could not be conveniently crossed by the second nicol. For this reason, the influence of very small concentrations of barium salt has been tried.

TABLE VII.

	Amount of 2% sol = 10 c.c.		Total vol. = 20 c.c.		
Barium nitrate (0.05%) c.c.	...	0	1.0	2.0	3.0
Shift	...	47	47	48	50
Relative birefringence	...	43.5	43.5	44.4	46.3

The influence of small amounts of barium nitrate is very slight; however, with increased concentrations, in its presence also, as in the case of potassium nitrate, the magnetic birefringence is considerably increased.

Magnetic birefringence according to the theory of Langevin is due to the combined magnetic and optical anisotropies of the molecules. In a magnetic field, the molecules try to set themselves in places of easiest magnetisability so far as the thermal agitations allow, and on account of this tendency, if the molecules are optically anisotropic also, the medium acquires a feeble birefringence. In the case of colloidal solutions, apart from the molecular anisotropy, a sort of structural anisotropy dependent on the nature of colloidal aggregation is also exhibited.

Unless under flow, the sol of mercurisulphosalicylic acid does not show any marked optical double refraction and as such, the values obtained under the influence of magnetic field show that the particles become orientated as soon as the field is applied. Thus it is a sort of magnetic analogue of rod-like double refraction, the theory of which has been developed by Wiener (*Ber. sachs. Akad. Wiss.*, 1909, 61, 113). The particles of the colloids showing magnetic double refraction are non-spherical and markedly elongated, and

they are orientated in a regular manner under the influence of mechanical flow, or in magnetic or electric fields. When some salt as potassium nitrate is added to the sol, the discharged units of the colloidal particles form highly elongated chains and hence the anisotropy is very much increased in its presence.

We could not observe any birefringence in the sols of ferric phosphate or zirconium hydroxide though these are also lyophilic and capable of giving jellies. Further work is in progress of magnetic birefringence of colloidal solutions.

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